

Media Analysis through Contrast Pattern Mining

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Abstract

Data mining aims at constructing models or finding interesting patterns. This paper presents a selection of data and text mining approaches for finding contrasting patterns in newspaper text corpora. This study analyzes a corpus of articles covering the 2007 Kenyan elections and post-election crisis, attempting to capture the differences between local (Kenyan) and Western (British and US) newspaper articles. We have first applied a contrast set mining method aimed at extracting contrasting patterns in articles of different news sources. We have also applied a tool for semi-automated topic ontology construction Ontogen, enforcing the separation into clusters of local and Western documents, and analyzed the keywords proposed by the Support Vector Machine classifier that best distinguish between the two classes. Next we used the same tool for finding the topics by k-means clustering of the entire document corpus and interpreted the contrasting words between local and Western views on each of these topics. The most interesting contrasting patterns reveal that, in contrast to local media, the Western press interpreted the elections from the ethnic perspective.

1. Introduction

Data mining aims at constructing models from large collections of data, or at finding interesting patterns in the data (Witten and Frank, 2005). Data mining can be viewed as a central step in the process of *knowledge discovery in databases* (KDD), where knowledge discovery refers to the overall process of discovering useful knowledge from data (Fayyad et al., 1996). The knowledge discovery process is a cooperative effort of humans and computers: humans select the data to be explored, define analysis problems, set goals and interpret the results, while computers search through the data looking for patterns and models that meet the human-defined goals. *Text mining* (Feldman and Sanger, 2007) is a variant of data mining in which models and patterns are extracted from unstructured natural language text.

Media analysis has been a topic of several studies, including the application of statistical and machine learning approaches to daily monitoring of news from different media in the Europe Media Monitor research and development project of the European Joint Research Center (<http://emm.newsbrief.eu/overview.html>) that gathers reports from news portals world-wide in 43 languages, classifies the articles, analyses the news texts by extracting information from them, aggregates the information, issues alerts and produces intuitive visual presentations of the information found. Text classification methods prove to be a useful vehicle e.g., for different newspaper article classification tasks, such as article genre, topic or author classification. The closest to our work is a media analysis study of Fortuna et al. (2008).

This paper explores a specific media analysis task, aimed at finding patterns that distinguish different document classes, such as journal articles published by different media when reporting about the 2007 Kenyan election crisis. We aim at finding differences between two selected classes in the corpus: local and Western journals. Two main methods for finding contrasting patterns are adopted: contrast set mining (Bay and Pazzani, 2001) and semi-automatic topic ontology construction (Fortuna et al., 2007).

The starting hypothesis is that news coverage of Kenyan events is not the same in the Kenyan local and in the US and British Western press. We expect differences due to addressing different audiences, different ways of reporting, as well as some ideology-related differences, since reporting is never neutral: newsmakers always select the news, present and interpret the events, frequently from a particular ideological position (Fairclough, 1995). They write and report addressing their expected audiences and offer a frame of interpretation of events. Media power is generally symbolic and persuasive, in the sense that the media primarily have the potential to control to some extent the minds of readers or viewers, but not directly their actions (Van Dijk, 1995).

In the theory of linguistic pragmatics, using language is seen as a process of meaning generation characterized by the constant making of choices, where all (conscious and unconscious) lexical, syntactic or discursive choices, are considered to be significant and could have ideological implications (Verschueren 2008).

In this research, we show how text and data mining techniques can be used for detecting contrasting choices. In previous work (Pollak, 2009) we have proven that differences in local and Western reporting can be approached as data mining classification task, generating classification models with 90% accuracy and providing interesting insight into the data. In current paper we use contrast set mining and text mining techniques to continue in this line of research.

We are aware that data and text mining models do not take into consideration the contexts in which the articles were originally produced and interpreted and therefore accentuate that these techniques are an interesting view of a corpus, which should be combined with further qualitative interpretations.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the data set, followed by applying a simple tag clouds approach, aimed at analyzing differences between the two groups of articles. Section 3 addresses a contrast set mining task where the goal is to find differences between groups of instances (Western and local articles). Section 4 addresses the same problem by a topic ontology construction approach, supported by the OntoGen tool.

2. Corpus description and exploration

This media analysis study concerns Kenyan presidential and parliamentary elections, held on December 27, 2007, and the crisis following the elections. Two main election candidates were incumbent president Mwai Kibaki and the opposition presidential candidate Raila Odinga. Odinga's party Orange Democratic Movement (ODM) won the parliamentary election against Kibaki's Party of National Unity (PNU). Kibaki is a member of the traditionally dominant Kikuyu ethnic group and Odinga is a member of the Luo ethnic group. Kibaki was declared the winner of presidential elections and swore in, despite Odinga's claims of victory. The election was followed by violence, riots and conflicts. The crisis ended in a power-sharing agreement, signed end of February 2008: Kibaki became the president, and Odinga the prime minister who swore in April 2008.

The original corpus was collected as part of the *Intertextuality and Flows of Information* project, led by the Center of Pragmatics, University of Antwerp. For our experiments we selected 464 articles (about 320,000 words) from six different daily newspapers in English, covering the time period from December 22, 2007 to February 29, 2008. The British and US press (*The Independent*, *The Times*, *The New York Times* and *The Washington Post*) that we label "Western" (WE) published 232 articles on the topic. In order to have a symmetrical corpus, we randomly selected 232 articles from the Kenyan, "local" newspapers (LO) *Daily Nation* and *The Standard*.

Since our aim is to better understand the way of reporting on the same events by different newspapers, we had to remove all information that could be distinctive for the two document classes, but not significant for our work. To illustrate, newspapers have normally only few journalists covering Kenya events; if their names were not removed, the author's name could easily be selected as a distinguishing feature.

Therefore, we removed meta-information such as newspaper source, authors of articles, dates of publication, names of photographers, mails of authors, types of articles, etc., and used only the remaining relevant data for document analysis (titles, text and photo descriptions).

In order to get an initial data understanding we used the most straightforward method for getting a "feel" of the contents of the data: the tag cloud representation of documents (<http://tagcrowd.com/>). As our goal was to find the differences between the local and Western articles, we constructed two separate tag cloud representations shown in Figure 2, one for each of the two classes (local and Western). Since we are interested in contrasting patterns, it is particularly interesting to pay attention to the words that are present in the cloud of only one of the classes. These distinguishing words are listed below:

Local:	added, commission, community, constitution, eck, house, Kenyans, mediation, meeting, members, minister, mp, national, ODM, office, peace, PNU, security, solution, state, support, team.
Western:	africa, areas, days, ethnic, kikuyu, live, luo, mwai, opposition, supporters, town, tribal, tribe, united, valley, week, Western, years.

Figure 1: Contrasting words

From a comparison between two tag clouds (Figures 2a and 2b) we can see that many key words are the same (which correspond to the expectation concerning the fact that they speak of the same topic). However, gap analysis (Figure 1) can lead to understanding of differences which show different perspectives on the reported events.

The most interesting observations are that in the local press we do not find any references to the ethnicity, while in the Western press the words *ethnic*, *tribe*, *Kikuyu* and *Luo* are part of the tag cloud (i.e. between the most frequent words). Secondly, words appearing only in local press are more of political frame, e.g. *ODM* and *PNU* (the main two political parties), *eck* (standing for Electoral Commission of Kenya) *mp*, *commission*, *community*, *constitution*, *mediation*, *meeting*, *peace*, *security*, *solution*.

Figure 2: Tag cloud interpretation

3. Contrast Pattern Mining

Finding contrasting patterns is one of fundamental tasks in data analysis as it aims at finding differences between instances of different groups. This descriptive data mining task, where groups of labeled examples are given and the goal is to find differences between the groups, is known as *contrast set mining* (CSM) (Bay and Pazzani, 2001). Specifically, CSM is defined as finding “conjunctions of attributes and values that differ meaningfully in their distributions across groups.” In this paper, a *subgroup discovery* (SD) method was applied to discover contrasting descriptions of groups of documents of the given class (LO or WE), as it was shown in (Kralj Novak et al., 2009) that each CSM task can be adequately translated to a SD task. A SD task aims at constructing rules describing a group of instances of the target class, which is as large as possible and has the most unusual statistical distribution of the target class (Wrobel, 1997).

For the task of contrast set mining, we used SD algorithm (Gamberger and Lavrač, 2002) implemented as Orange¹ web service (Podpečan et al., 2010). For data representation, we built feature vectors of 500 attributes (word unigrams) ranked by chi square test. The feature values are binary (1 - word is present in the document, and 0 - word is not present in the document). A selection of best contrasting patterns (subgroups) for each class is shown in Figure 3 (all rules have high coverage of positive examples of the target class only).

- 1) $kikuyu = 1 \ \& \ odm = 0 \Rightarrow WE$ (TP=114, FP=0)
- 2) $kikuyu = 1 \ \& \ post\text{-}election = 0 \Rightarrow WE$ (TP=96, FP=0)
- 3) $kikuyu = 1 \ \& \ mr = 0 \Rightarrow class = WE$ (TP=89, FP=0)
- 4) $dr = 1 \ \& \ seems = 0 \ \& \ odm = 1 \Rightarrow LO$ (TP=51, FP=0)

Figure 3: Selection of contrasting rules. TP (true positives) and FP (false positives) show the number of positive and negative examples respectively.

The analysis shows that all the contrasting patterns discovered for class WE involve the word *Kikuyu*, and are characterized by the absence of words: *ODM*, *post-election* and *Mr* respectively. Rule 1 covering a lot of WE examples says that Western press uses word *Kikuyu* but not the abbreviation *ODM*. The simplest interpretation can be done in terms of different backgrounds of addressed readers: Orange Democratic Movement party’s abbreviation for Western readers bears no meaning and was avoided by Western journalists, whereas explaining who belongs to *Kikuyu* is not needed for Kenyan readers. However, in the corpus we discover that the name of the party is not a very unbalanced feature only in its abbreviated form, but also when named *Orange Democratic Movement*. This leads to a hypothesis that Western media prefer to present the Kenyan elections in terms of conflicts between different ethnic groups and not in terms of political parties (cf. tag cloud representations in Figure 2).

Rule 3 indicates that when Western press focuses on the main ethnic group (*Kikuyu*), it does not mention many protagonists, which could be introduced by title *Mr*. The interpretation of events as a *post-election* crisis or violence is specific to local press (cf. second part of Rule 2).

¹ <http://www.ailab.si/orange/>

Based on Rule 4 it would be interesting to explore the way of attributing the sentences to different sources when reporting. It is possible that the presence of *Dr* and the absence of *seems* indicate that local media use more often reported speech, attributing opinions to different sources (we list some examples from the local part of the corpus: *Dr Kofi Annan said; Dr Condoleezza Rice cleared the air over; Dr Alfred Mutua said*), while Western media often use sentences without mentioning the exact source (some examples from Western press: *It all seems likely to get worse; Mr. Odinga seems different; the election seems to have tapped into an atavistic vein of tribal tension*).

4. Contrasting keyword detection

In computer science the term *ontology* denotes a formal representation of a set of concepts of a domain and the relationships among these concepts. Ontologies are organized hierarchically: a concept is divided into a set of sub-concepts. A concept representing a set of documents can be also described by the main topics addressed in the documents. Accordingly, a *topic ontology* (Fortuna, 2007) is a hierarchical organization of documents’ topics and their sub-topics.

Semi-automatic topic ontology construction tool OntoGen (<http://ontogen.ijs.si/>) (Fortuna, 2007) is mainly used for building topic ontologies from unlabeled data, but can be used also for document classification, search, etc. OntoGen is a semi-automatic tool, because it actively supports the user in the ontology construction process.

In OntoGen, hierarchical decomposition of a given set of documents into document subsets is performed by *k*-means clustering and each sub-domain (sub-concepts) is described by the main topics that the documents cover.

OntoGen offers two different ways of getting the topic descriptions. Using the first one (Keywords), the list of keywords is composed of most descriptive words for the document cluster: i.e., *n* most frequent keywords describing the centroid of the document cluster. Using the second one (SVM Keywords), the list of keywords is composed of most contrasting words, best distinguishing the selected concept (document cluster) from its sibling concepts in the hierarchy, where the distinguishing keywords are extracted by the Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier.

This section describes how OntoGen tool (Fortuna et al. 2007) was used for detecting the differences between the local and the Western press.

The goal of the first experiment was to see which are the subtopics of the local and Western coverage of Kenyan election and post-election crisis. We first created the local and Western category and categorized the documents inside these two categories. We observe the distinguishing keywords, selected by the SVM algorithm implemented in OntoGen, for the local and Western class, respectively. The SVM-based contrasting keywords, best distinguishing between the articles of the two classes, are presented below:

Local:	odm, mp, team, mr, pn, odm_leader, president kibaki, dr, media, statement
Western:	kikuyu, mr_kibaki, opposition, mr_odinga, lu, tribe, tribalism, opposition_leader, odinga, ethnic

Figure 4: SVM keywords

These patterns show the difference in a way of referring to main protagonists: local articles use *ODM leader* and *President Kibaki*, while Western media call them *Mr Kibaki*, *Mr Odinga* and *opposition leader*. Local media mention political parties and functions: *ODM*, *PNU* and *MP*, while Western media present the election through the ethnic aspect *Kikuyu*, *Luo*, *ethnic*, and use even ideologically marked words *tribe* or *tribalism*. The ideological aspects of these stereotyping interpretation frameworks can be found also in Ray (2008).

In the last experiment we analyzed the differences in sub-concepts suggested by OntoGen for the whole data set through differences in topics covered by local and Western media. In Figure 5 we can find four different automatically extracted topics, number of all articles for each topic, number of articles by class, and contrasting keywords. The number of articles informs us which topics were more frequently addressed in the Western and in the local articles. The focus on “Kikuyu, police and town” (Topic 1) and on the two main political candidates (Topic 2) is typical for WE. On the other hand, when the articles talk about ODM, member of the parliament or police the articles are nearly exclusively from LO. Also talking about the Annan’s mediation team is the local angle. The SVM keywords can be understood as different views on the same topic e.g. for Topic 1, covering the violence and crisis, the Western media adopt ethnic frame, while Kenyan press is concerned about the consequences of the violence for the people (*child*, *victim*, *camp*).

Topic	Contrasting SVM keywords	
Topic 1: (135 art.) kikuyu, police, town	WE (101 art.): kikuyu, opposition, luo, ethnic, tribe, protest, valley, rift_valley, kalenjin, burn	LO (34 art.): youth, child, victim, town, food, estate, resident, kisumu, camp, road
Topic 2: (154 art.) mr kibaki, mr odinga, mr	WE (110 art.): mr_kibaki, mr_odinga, opposition, kikuyu, tribalism, odinga, voting, power, opposition_leader, kibaki	LO (44 art.): media, risk, appeal, statement, concern, editor, ranneberger, crisis, provide, report
Topic 3: (87 art.) odm, mp, police	WE (3 art.): mungiki, embakusus, protect, ballot, secret, left, bloodshed, apply, duty, clerk	LO (84 art.): odm, mp, police, mr, party, court, house, law, office, pnu
Topic 4: (88 art.) annan, talk, odm	WE (18 art.): opposition, annan, deal, mr_annan, talk, prime_minister, agree, opposition_leader, prime, mr_kibaki	LO (70 art.): odm, team, pnu, solution, mediation, proposal, discuss, meeting, mr, president_kibaki

Figure 5: Analysis of differences between local and Western coverage of same (automatically generated) topics.

5. Conclusions

The topic of this study is the analysis of the articles covering the 2007 Kenyan elections and post-election crisis, aimed at capturing the differences between local (Kenyan) and Western (British and US) newspaper articles. The main motivation was to use quantitative methods as a starting point for finding interesting observations for further qualitative discourse analysis (we are currently preparing joint article with R. Coesemans from Antwerp Center of Pragmatics).

For finding contrasting patterns, differentiating between the local and Western media, we adopted several methods. Firstly, a simple tag cloud representation offered a basic view of the corpus. Since we were analyzing the articles covering the same topic, the majority of the words were the same. However, words with different weight and specially those present only in one of the two tag clouds were of special interest. The two main methods for finding contrasting patterns, differentiating between the local and Western media were contrast set mining and semi-automated topic ontology construction. We applied also SVM contrasting keywords detection. The study shows that meaningful contrasting patterns can be detected by the proposed methodology and show that the ethnic and tribal aspects are the frameworks of interpretation of crisis in Western media, while political angle is more typical in local media.

6. References

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